

Development of Material Process for High-Entropy Ceramic Matrix Composites using CALPHAD

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Introduction

Requirement for advanced heat resistant material

Hypersonic vehicles cruising at >M5

Aerodynamic heating for components

$$T = T_0 \left(1 + r \frac{1-\gamma}{2} M^2 \right) \quad T \sim 2000^\circ\text{C} @ >M5$$

T_0 : initial temp., r : recovery factor
 γ : heat capacity ratio, M : Mach number

Conventional attractive candidate:
Ultra High Temperature Ceramics (UHTC) + SiC

✓ Materials with high melting point (>2500°C)
+ barrier for oxygen diffusion (SiO₂)

✗ Active oxidation of SiC (SiC → SiO(g)) at above 1800°C

Advanced aerospace heat resistant materials without containing Si is required for applying at above 1800°C

The introduction of "high entropy (HE)" to ceramic matrix

Ceramic composites with HE ceramic matrix is expected to show unique properties with extreme high heat resistance!

Objective

Development of alloy melt-infiltration (MI) method by using CALPHAD to fabricated carbon fiber reinforced refractory high-entropy ceramic matrix composites as a novel candidate for Si-free heat resistant material

Materials and procedure

Alloy design by CALPHAD

Fabrication of C/RHECs

Arc-jet test

Results and Discussion

Observation and analyses of as-infiltrated material

Observation and analyses of C/RHECs after oxidation

Summary

Oxidation rate of C/RHECs was suppressed compared to some C/UHTCs

Carbon fiber contained refractory High-entropy ceramic matrix composites (C/RHECs) was successfully fabricated by high-entropy alloy melt-infiltration designed by using calculation thermodynamics. Oxidation rate of C/RHECs at 1800-1900°C was lower than or almost the same as Si containing UHTC composites. It was clearly indicated that Si containing materials are not always necessary for heat resistant materials exposed at above 1800°C in oxidizing atmosphere.

High-entropy ceramics was successfully formed as matrices of C/RHECs